

THE PHENOMENON OF POLISEMY AT THE SEMANTIC LEVEL OF WORDS

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Abstract: This article discusses the concept of polysemy, its types and how it differs in contexts. It deals with the study of the specific features of phraseological polysemy in the English and Uzbek languages, their comparative-typological analysis is discussed, and some examples are given.

Key words: phraseological polysemy, lexicology, lexical polysemy, monosemy, diachronic, synchronic, simple and complex polisemantik words, derivative meaning of the word.

Semasiology is a branch of lexicology that studies the structural meaning of words and related phenomena. Some words have only one lexical meaning, while some have two or more lexical meanings. Based on this, they are divided into two types:

1. Monosemy is the fact that words have only one lexical meaning;
2. Polysemy is the phenomenon of presence of two or more lexical meanings in words [3].

All language units are divided into two groups, monosemantic and polysemantic, from which polysemantic language units need to be studied separately. Polysemy is characteristic of both lexical units and grammatical units.

Polysemy is commonly encountered in everyday language. For instance:

1. **"Paper"** can refer to a thin material made from cellulose pulp, a newspaper, an academic article, or a set of examination questions.
2. **"Head"** can mean the upper part of the human body, the top or front of something, a person in charge, or the froth on top of a glass of beer.
3. **"Bank"** can signify a financial institution, the land alongside a body of water, or a set in a row (as in a "bank of lights").

It is known that the lexical and grammatical types of polysemy in the Uzbek language differ. Lexical polysemy is a phenomenon of polysemy in lexical units, in which a new figurative meaning is formed on the basis of the original logical meaning of the word. For example, the meaning of the word "head" is "the part of the human body above the neck"; 2. Like "brain" (his head works well). Grammatical polysemy means multiple meanings of one grammatical element. In this case, one grammatical form adapts to the meaning of the word it is combined with and creates different meanings.

There are two types of lexical polysemy: 1. Lexical polysemy - the phenomenon of polysemy in words: the word 'Picture' has 9 different meanings. For example, She is the picture of her mother - in this sentence, picture means a copy, that is, it comes in the sense of 'her mother's cousin, she looks like her mother', and again to form a clear picture of smth - like making an exact copy of something. 2. Phraseological polysemy is the phenomenon of polysemy in expressions: to stand out 1- "to be known", "to stand out" 2- "to attract attention".

Monosemy is characteristic of the period of initial use of a newly created word and a newly assimilated word. Terms are also usually monosemantic.

Monosemantic words include conditional nouns. Every word is monosemantic by creating a word. Later, it serves as a name for other phenomena, thereby changing and developing its meaning. As a result, various changes occur in the meaning of the word, so as a result, a monosemantic word turns into a polysemantic word. Lexical polysemy is a multifaceted and complex phenomenon. Developing the lexical meaning of almost every word requires a concrete, individual approach. Therefore, it is very difficult to define and systematize lexical meanings. General ideas about the polysemy of the word usually serve only to create an idea about the development of the lexical meaning of the word. Polysyllabic words are divided into two types according to whether or not they can perform the function of another set of lexical meanings.

- 1) simple polysemantic words;
- 2) complex polysemantic words;

The lexical meanings of simple polysemantic words serve only as a category to which they belong. They include all polysemantic words related to Uzbek verbs and pronouns. That is, the lexical meanings of words belonging to the group of verbs and pronouns do not perform the function of another group. This idea is not difficult to understand if it is explained in ambiguous words related to the verb group. Because the

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words related to the verb group usually have their own form in Turkic languages, they are in their pure form and do not accept the forms of other categories, and also do not perform the functions of other categories.

It should be noted that the verb does not perform the function of any other category according to its lexical meaning in the case of a pure verb without entering into any special form. If it is one of the special forms of the verb: adjective, adverb, or verb, it becomes a different category. In any case, it is characteristic of the inflected form of the verb. For example: Today most people are working hard in order to live better life. In this example, to live is the name of an action, and it is performing the function of another category, i.e. case. It should be explained in a different way that the words related to the pronoun category do not appear in another category of lexical meanings. Because the word belonging to the pronoun family is replaced by another word family. The lexical meanings contained in it can fulfill the task of different categories. For example: My mum bought me a dress. Claire is so smart girl and she has great imagination - 'Claire is so smart girl and she has great imagination'.

But they are abstract and do not express concepts directly, but point to it or because they indicate it, remain characteristic of the pronoun group. It can be seen that all polysemantic words in the group of verbs and pronouns are simple polysemantic words.

Complex polysemantic words are observed in words related to adjectives, numbers and nouns. Simple polysemantic words are rarely found among the polysemantic words of the adjective and adverbial group. Because the words of these two categories almost always mean the same sign, and they exchange their tasks. For example, white collar "servant", white race "white road", white house "white house", white lie "innocent mistake", white witch "kind witch". The lie which you've told us in the way of goodness is white. "It is not your fault that you lied to us in the name of goodness." In this sentence, white is used not as a determiner, but as a participle. The phenomenon of polysemy in English is a comprehensive phenomenon, and it is approached from two perspectives: diachronic and synchronic. Changing the semantic structure of a word requires diachronic learning. Diachronically polysemy indicates that a word retains its original meaning and at the same time acquires one or other new meanings.

The diachronic semantic analysis of the polysemantic English word "table" revealed that it is equivalent to its original meaning in Old English (a flat slab of stone

or wood), and the rest of the derived meanings are they are derived from the original meaning.

A synchronic approach to polysemy means the co-occurrence of different meanings of one word in a certain historical period and the combination of these meanings in the semantic structure of the word.

After all, a word is the most variable unit among linguistic units, its meanings develop over time, and as a result, new derived meanings appear around the main meaning. Almost every word has its own artificial meanings, in some cases the main meaning loses its importance as a result of the emergence of derivative meanings. The change in word meanings is a hotly debated topic that has attracted many linguists. When we talk about the meanings of words, opposite concepts called permanent, stable and changing meanings arise. Some meanings are characterized by stability and immutability, while some meanings change over time. They appear only in certain contexts and this meaning is not recorded in dictionaries. The main and derived meanings are distinguished by their relative invariability, therefore they also form the semantic structure of the word and are recorded in dictionaries. The problem of ambiguity is one of the most discussed problems in lexicology. Sometimes it is not possible to distinguish an independent word from the derived meaning of a polysemous word, that is, the semantic connection between the derived meaning and the main meaning is broken, and as a result, it becomes a homonym of the word it is made of.

Polysemy is one of the special categories of lexicology. Each polysemantic word has its own stylistic features, and the analysis of lexical meanings in its dictionary meaning requires a lot of research and observation. Context is important for the meaning of polysemantic words to emerge. Because polysemantic words have several lexical meanings, but participate in the context with only one meaning. In English, unlike Uzbek, the contexts that determine the meaning of a polysemantic word are divided into three categories:

a. Lexical context; b. Grammatical context; d. Extralinguistic context. Lexical groups with polysemantic words occupy the main place in the lexical context. For this, let's analyze the word heavy polysemantically. The original meaning of the word Heavy is heavy. But if it is used with a lexical group denoting natural phenomena, the meaning of "strong" arises: heavy wind, heavy storm. Or, if it occurs in compounds such as heavy industry, heavy artillery, the meaning is translated as heavy (heavy industry, heavy artillery).

In a grammatical context, the grammatical construction of a text or context helps determine the meaning of a polysemantic word. For example, the main meaning of the word make is to build, to do. But its meaning to urge, to force appears only in the grammatical device / to make + subject + infinitive /. For example, to make smb laugh, work. Or the meaning of this word to become part occurs only in the grammatical structure / to make+adjective+noun/. For example, to make a good wife, a devoted teacher.

In addition, English also has an extralinguistic or situational context. Sometimes the meaning of a polysemantic word is not known either in the lexical context or in the grammatical context. In this case, we can only determine the meaning of the polysemantic word in the intended situation. For example, the meaning of the polysemantic word ring in the combination to give smb a ring is determined not by the lexical or grammatical context, but by the situational context. The polysemantic word ring has the dictionary meaning of circle, ring, call, and to give smb a ring also means 'to call someone', 'to give someone a ring' means The exact meaning of the combination is known only depending on the situation in which it is spoken. This is an important function of extralinguistic or situational context. Phraseological units in each language have their own linguistic features. But in all languages, phraseological units serve as language wealth. Polysemantic phraseological units serve to enrich the lexical structure of the language and speech, and emotional coloring embodies meanings.

In conclusion, polysemy and related research results have been interpreted differently in different system languages. The phenomenon of polysemy occurs in almost all (verb, pronoun, noun, adjective, number and adverb) word groups. Nouns, numbers have been studied a lot, pronouns, adverbs and verbs have been studied less. The study of this leads to the difference between the English and Uzbek languages.

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